

Supplementary material information

Title: Ambient air pollution and depression – A protocol for a systematic review and meta-analysis

Included files:

Appendix A. Search terms for each database

Appendix B. Quality assessment scheme adapted from OHAT Risk of Bias Assessment Tool.

Appendix C. Data extraction table adapted from Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of interventions.

Appendix A. Search terms for each database

Search terms
<p>Pubmed</p> <p>(((((("Environmental Pollutants"[Mesh]) OR ("Environmental Pollution"[Mesh])) OR ("Nitrogen Oxides"[Mesh])) OR ("Particulate Matter"[Mesh])) OR ("Ozone"[Mesh])) OR ("Soot"[Mesh])) OR (((((((((((((((("air pollution"[Title/Abstract]) OR ("air pollutant*"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("environmental pollutant*"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("environmental pollution"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("environmental exposure*"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("nitrogen dioxide"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("nox"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("no2"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("nitrogen oxide*"[Title/Abstract])) OR (ozone[Title/Abstract])) OR ("o3"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("particulate matter"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm2.5"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm2,5"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm 2.5"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm 2,5"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm10"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("pm 10"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("black carbon"[Title/Abstract])) AND ((((((("Mood Disorders"[Mesh]) OR ("Depression"[Mesh])) OR (depression[Title/Abstract])) OR (depressed[Title/Abstract])) OR (depressive[Title/Abstract])) OR ("mood disorder*"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("affective disorder*"[Title/Abstract]))</p>
<p>Embase</p> <p>((('air pollution'/exp OR 'ozone'/exp OR 'particulate matter'/exp OR 'soot'/exp OR 'nitrogen dioxide'/exp OR 'nitrogen oxide'/exp) OR ('air pollution':ab,ti OR 'environmental pollution':ab,ti OR 'nitrogen dioxide':ab,ti OR 'ozone':ab,ti OR 'o3':ab,ti OR 'particulate matter':ab,ti OR 'pm2.5':ab,ti OR 'pm2,5':ab,ti OR 'pm 2.5':ab,ti OR 'pm 2,5':ab,ti OR 'pm10':ab,ti OR 'pm 10':ab,ti OR 'soot':ab,ti OR 'black carbon':ab,ti OR 'nox':ab,ti OR 'no2':ab,ti OR 'air pollutant*':ab,ti OR 'environmental pollutant*':ab,ti OR 'environmental exposure*':ab,ti OR 'nitrogen oxide*':ab,ti)) AND ('depression'/exp OR 'mood disorder'/exp OR depression:ab,ti OR depressive:ab,ti OR depressed:ab,ti OR 'mood disorder*':ab,ti OR 'affective disorder*':ab,ti)</p>

Web of science:

AB=("environmental pollutant*") OR AB=("air pollutant*") OR AB=("air pollution") OR AB=("environmental pollution") OR AB=("nitrogen oxide*") OR AB=("nitrogen dioxide") OR AB=(NO2) OR AB=(NOx) OR AB=(Ozone) OR AB=(O3) OR AB=("particulate matter") OR AB=("pm2.5") OR AB=("pm2,5") OR AB=("pm 2,5") OR AB=("pm 2.5") OR AB=("pm10") OR AB=("pm 10") OR AB=("black carbon") AND AB=("mood disorder*") OR AB=("affective disorder*") OR AB=(depression) OR AB=(depressive) OR AB=(depressed)

Scopus:

((ABS ("black carbon")) OR (ABS ("pm 10")) OR (ABS ("pm10")) OR (ABS ("pm 2,5")) OR (ABS ("pm 2.5")) OR (ABS ("pm2,5")) OR (ABS ("pm2.5")) OR (ABS ("particulate matter")) OR (ABS ("o3")) OR (ABS ("ozone")) OR (ABS ("nox")) OR (ABS ("nitrogen oxide*")) OR (ABS ("no2")) OR (ABS ("nitrogen dioxide")) OR (ABS ("environmental exposure*")) OR (ABS ("environmental pollution")) OR (ABS ("environmental pollutant*")) OR (ABS ("air pollutant*")) OR (ABS ("air pollution"))) AND ((ABS (depression)) OR (ABS (depressed)) OR (ABS ("mood disorder*")) OR (ABS (depressive)) OR (ABS ("affective disorder*"))))

Quality Assessment Scheme adapted from OHAT.

Answer format:

ROB will be categorized as definitely low ROB (++) , probably low ROB (+) , probably high ROB (- or not reported “NR”) , or definitely high ROB (-) for each criterion (OHAT, 2015)

Appendix B. Quality assessment scheme adapted from OHAT Risk of Bias Assessment Tool.

Bias item	Risk of Bias criteria	Answer
<p>Selection bias</p>	<p>Does selection of study participants result in appropriate comparison groups? This alludes to achieving comparable baseline characteristics among groups regarding factors related to the outcome measures of interest, excluding the exposures under investigation.</p> <p>Subjects, both those exposed and non-exposed, should be alike in various aspects: recruited from the same eligible population, enlisted using comparable ascertainment methods with consistent inclusion and exclusion criteria, and shared similar age and health statuses. They should also be recruited within the same time frame and exhibited comparable participation/response rates.</p>	<p>Low risk bias: There is direct evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were met.</p> <p>Probably low risk: There is indirect evidence that the bias criteria for this domain was met. The difference between the groups would not significantly bias results.</p> <p>Probably high risk: There is indirect evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were not met. <i>Or</i> there is missing information about the comparisons group without explanation.</p> <p>High risk: There is direct evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were not met.</p>

**Detection bias,
exposure
assessment**

Can we be confident in the exposure characterization?

Assurance regarding exposure demands the utilization of reliable, valid, and sensitive exposure measurement methods consistently administered across all groups. Exposure misclassification or measurement error may either occur independently of the outcomes (non-differential) or be correlated with the outcome of interest (differential).

Major considerations

- Exposure measurement models should be enhanced by inclusive measurements, incorporating representative data such as traffic patterns and other geographical indicators of air pollution.
- The residential address or within a small area of the residence, should be used to predict the air pollution levels. Exposure is estimated at the study participant's physical location, e.g. residence. If exposure is modelled on larger geographical units, such as zip-codes, municipalities, or grid-cells. Used units are in a resolution high enough to estimate reliable exposures and exposure contrasts.
- Spatial resolution information of models was provided.
- Air pollutant measurements/model estimations should be at least on daily resolution with limited missing data (<25%).

Low risk bias: There is direct evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were met. Exposure was measured individually (i.e. study participants wearing sensors), or estimated based on linking a precise representative location of the study participant (i.e., residential addresses) with an air pollution model.

Probably low risk: There is indirect evidence the bias criteria for this domain were met. OR the exposure measurements were acquired indirectly through methods that have been validated direct air quality measurements (i.e, inter-method validation). Exposure is not assessed based on a precise location, but the geographical unit of exposure modelling is small enough to reliably detect differences between exposures (examples: street blocks, small postcode areas).

Probably high risk: There is indirect evidence that the exposure measurements did not meet the risk of bias criteria for this domain. OR there is direct evidence of use of non-validated methods for exposure measurements. OR inadequate information provided regarding the validity and reliability of the exposure measurement method (i.e., simple geographical interpolation of measured air pollution).

		<p>High risk: There is direct evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were not met. OR evidence of misclassification OR The exposure unit is not small enough to reliably detect differences between exposures (examples: regions, large postcode areas, states).</p>
<p>Detection bias, outcome assessment</p>	<p>Can we be confident in the outcome assessment? Ensuring confidence in the outcome involves employing methods that are valid, reliable, and sensitive to assess the outcome consistently across all groups. Outcome is classified based on standard diagnostic criteria (International Classification of Diseases or of Primary Care) and provided by a national or regional database (gold standard). Misclassification or measurement error of the outcome may be either unrelated to the exposure (non-differential) or associated with the exposure (differential).</p> <p>3 essential factors for evaluating bias in the outcome assessment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outcome assessment should be objective. - consistency of the outcome measurement. - The outcome assessors should be blinded in terms of knowledge of the exposure status. 	<p>Low risk bias: There is direct evidence that the bias criteria for this domain were met. AND Participants have been followed the same amount of time across all groups.</p> <p>Probably low risk: There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assess using reliable and valid methods, however, not the gold standard (validity and reliability lower than the gold standard). AND Participants have been followed the same amount of time across all groups. AND there is direct evidence that the outcome assessors were blinded in terms of exposure status.</p> <p>Probably high risk: There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assess using a method with no information regarding validity. OR different follow-up time length across groups. OR there is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors could infer exposure status prior to outcome reporting.</p>

		<p>High risk. There is direct evidence that the outcome assessment was conducted using insensitive method. OR direct evidence for outcome assessors could infer exposure status prior to outcome reporting.</p>
	<p>Does the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables? Valid and reliable measurements were employed to evaluate primary covariates and confounders. Additionally, in the final analyses, measures were taken to account for these primary factors and potential biases through statistical methodologies such as standardization, matching, adjustment in multivariate models, stratification, propensity scoring, or other justified methods, thus minimizing research-specific biases.</p> <p>Essential potential confounders include age, sex, smoking, physical activity, urbanicity (or population density), covariate regarding socioeconomic status (e.g., education, occupation, income). Other potential confounders include season, ethnicity, time spent outside or at work and meteorological factors (e.g. temperature, relative humidity, barometric pressure, sunlight hours, and wind speed),</p>	<p>Low risk bias: the study accounted for all the essential potential confounders.</p> <p>Probably low risk: The study accounted for most of the essential confounders. And the lack of these confounders does likely not introduce noticeable bias.</p> <p>Probably high risk: The study is missing some essential confounders and lack of these could introduce bias.</p> <p>High risk: The study is did not address a majority of essential confounder.</p>
<p>Attrition/exclusion bias</p>	<p>Are outcome data complete without attrition or exclusion from analysis? Participants who discontinue their involvement in the study or become lost to follow-up may display distinct characteristics compared to those who continue their participation. The handling of subject exclusions in the analyses is sufficiently addressed, and clear documentation is provided for the reasons behind subject removal or exclusion from the analyses.</p>	<p>Low risk bias: There is direct evidence that indicates participant loss was managed effectively, and explanations for their removal from the study were provided. OR Appropriate methods were employed to assign missing data, ensuring that the characteristics of subjects lost to follow-up</p>

	<p>The greater the ratio of participants with missing data to those experiencing events, the higher the potential for bias.</p> <p>Important factors when assessing attrition are minimal: reasons for missing subjects are unlikely to be linked with the outcome and missing outcome data are evenly distributed among study groups, with comparable explanations for missing data across groups, no statistical difference in those lost-to-follow up and the study participants.</p>	<p>or with unavailable records were described in a consistent manner. Notably, these characteristics did not significantly differ from those of the study participants.</p> <p>Probably low risk There is indirect evidence that indicates participant loss was managed effectively, and explanations for their removal from the study were provided. OR those lost to follow-up were considered not significantly bias the results.</p> <p>Probably high risk: There are indirect evidence suggesting that the loss to follow-up was unacceptably high, or the information provided about the numbers of participants lost to follow-up was insufficient.</p> <p>High risk: There is direct evidence suggests that the loss of participants was unacceptably high and not sufficiently addressed.</p>
<p>Selective reporting</p>	<p>Were all measured outcomes reported?</p> <p>Selective reporting arises when pre-specified outcomes are either unreported or reported only partially. This is challenging to investigate entirely unless a study protocol is accessible or published. Assessing selective reporting bias involves comparing the information presented in the "methods" and "results" sections of the study, while also evaluating outcomes measured considering existing knowledge in the field.</p>	<p>Low risk bias: There is direct evidence of pre-specified outcomes were all reported.</p> <p>Probably low risk: There is inadequate information on selective outcome to be able to decide on low risk but there is indirect evidence of pre-specified outcomes were all reported.</p>

		<p>Probably high risk: There is inadequate information on selective outcome to be able to decide on high risk but there is indirect evidence of pre-specified outcomes were not all reported.</p> <p>High risk: There is direct evidence of pre-specified outcomes were not all reported</p>
<p>Other risk of bias</p>	<p>Were there no other potential threats to internal validity? Other potential threats to internal validity could include: The suitability of the statistical analyses employed, did the study adhere to the protocol, are there potential conflicts of interest among the author group, has the study be accused of being fraudulent?</p>	<p>Low risk bias: No indication for other source for bias.</p> <p>Probably low risk: There is indirect evidence to suggest the study was free from other source for bias.</p> <p>Probably high risk: There is indirect evidence to suggest that study was not free from other source for bias.</p> <p>High risk: There is direct evidence suggesting at least one significant source for bias</p>

OHAT. (2015). *OHAT Risk of Bias Rating Tool for Human and Animal Studies*. Institute of Environmental Health Sciences, US Department of Health and Human

Services. https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/sites/default/files/ntp/ohat/pubs/riskofbiastool_508.pdf

Appendix C. Data extraction table adapted from Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of interventions.

General information	
Study ID	
List authors	
The corresponding authors contacts details	
Title of article	
Name of journal	
Year of publication	
Digital object identifier (DOI)	
Country in which the study is conducted	
Study design	
Aim of study	
Study design	<input type="checkbox"/> Cohort/follow-up <input type="checkbox"/> Case-control <input type="checkbox"/> Cross-sectional <input type="checkbox"/> Randomized trial <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Study period (specify beginning and ending month)	
Study population	
Population description	
Inclusion criteria	
Exclusion criteria	
Country of study population	
Recruitment method	
Exposure assessment	
Type of exposure	<input type="checkbox"/> PM2.5

	<input type="checkbox"/> PM10 <input type="checkbox"/> Nitrogen dioxide (NO ₂) <input type="checkbox"/> Ozone (O ₃) <input type="checkbox"/> Black carbon (BC) <input type="checkbox"/> Sulfur dioxide (SO ₂) <input type="checkbox"/> Carbon monoxide (CO) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Mode of exposure data collection	
Duration of exposure	<input type="checkbox"/> Short term (≤ 30 days) <input type="checkbox"/> Long term (> 30 days)
Outcome Assessment	
Outcome definition (Criteria for diagnosis)	
Mode of outcome data collection	
Results	
Total number of participants	
Statistical model	
Covariates adjusted for (confounders)	
Effect measure type	<input type="checkbox"/> RR <input type="checkbox"/> OR <input type="checkbox"/> HR <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please specify)
Point estimate with lower and upper confidence interval	
Comments:	